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**DIGITALIZING THE CHEMISTRY LAB: EDUCATIONAL PLATFORMS AS A
TOOL FOR INTERACTIVE EXPERIMENTS IN GRADES 7–8**

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Annotation: *This article examines the potential of digital educational platforms in teaching chemistry to students in 7th- and 8th-grade students. The use of virtual laboratories and interactive simulation tools is shown to increase student engagement and facilitate understanding of chemical phenomena. In addition, interactive experiments contribute to the development of students' research skills. The article describes examples of educational platforms that can be used in chemistry lessons and their pedagogical impact on the learning process. Keywords: digital educational technologies, chemistry teaching, virtual laboratory, interactive experiments, secondary school chemistry.*

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Introduction. Currently, the integration of information and digital technologies in the education system is rapidly expanding. Particularly in science education, the introduction of new technologies makes it possible to increase the efficiency of the learning process. Practical work plays a particularly important role in chemistry education. Through laboratory experiments, students observe chemical reactions, study the properties of substances, and connect theoretical knowledge with practice [1].

However, within school environments it is not always possible to conduct all chemical experiments. In some cases, the lack of necessary equipment or reagents, as well as safety requirements, may prevent experiments from being carried out. In such situations, one of the effective solutions is the use of educational platforms. These platforms make it possible to model chemical processes virtually and allow students to conduct research in an interactive format. Scientific studies show that the use of multimedia and interactive learning materials increases students' interest in the subject and improves the learning comprehension. Interactive educational platforms are special digital environments that allow chemical processes to be presented in digital form and enable virtual experiments. One of the important features of such platforms is the visualization of chemical phenomena at the molecular level. This helps students better understand the structure of substances and the mechanisms of chemical reactions [2].

According to scientific research, visually presented information improves memory and comprehension. This is especially important in chemistry because many processes occur at the submicroscopic level and cannot be observed directly. In addition, interactive simulations allow students to change experimental parameters. For example, they can modify concentration, temperature, or the amount of reagents and observe the results. This approach corresponds to the inquiry-based learning method, which is considered one of the most effective pedagogical approaches in science education [3].

Materials and Methods. One of the most commonly used platforms in chemistry teaching is PhET Interactive Simulations. This project was developed at the University of Colorado in the USA (Figure 1).

Figure 1. PhET Interactive Simulations

The PhET platform contains many interactive models in chemistry, physics, and biology. They allow students to understand complex scientific concepts visually. For example, the pH scale simulation allows students to study the acidity of different solutions. Students can add various substances to the solution in a virtual environment and observe how the pH value changes [4].

Through this experiment, students can understand:

- the concept of acids and bases;
- the meaning of the pH scale;
- the effect of solution concentration.

Research shows that the use of PhET simulations improves students' understanding of scientific concepts.

2) Another effective platform is the Labster virtual laboratory (Figure 2). This platform allows students to conduct experiments in an environment similar to a real laboratory. In the virtual lab, students can work with different equipment, use reagents, and perform measurements [5].

Figure 2. Labster virtual laboratory

The main advantages of the Labster platform include:

- safety of experiments;
- the possibility of repeating experiments several times;
- visualization of chemical processes at the submicroscopic level.

Scientific studies state that virtual laboratories are effective tools that complement traditional laboratory work.

Organization of Interactive Experiments in 7–8 grades.

An example of using a digital platform in a chemistry lesson is presented below.

Lesson topic: «Acids and Bases»

Lesson objective: to determine the acidity of solutions and understand the meaning of the pH indicator.

Lesson Stages:

1. The teacher demonstrates an interactive model of the pH scale.
2. Students choose different substances (for example, lemon juice, water, soap solution).
3. Using a virtual indicator, students determine the pH level of each solution is determined.
4. The obtained results are analysed and conclusions are made.

During this activity, students:

- learn to observe the acidity of solutions;
- compare the properties of different substances;
- draw conclusions about acids and bases.

Such experiments develop students' research thinking and increase their interest in the subject.

The use of digital educational platforms in chemistry lessons has several important advantages. Interactive tasks and visual models make the learning process more engaging and increase students' interest in the subject. Virtual experiments also ensure safety, since some chemical reactions may be dangerous to perform in a real school laboratory. In addition, digital platforms make experiments more accessible, because students can conduct them even when laboratory equipment or reagents are limited. Another important advantage is the possibility of repeating experiments many times, which helps students better understand and remember the learning material [6].

Conclusion. The findings of this study indicate that the use of digital educational platforms is one of the most effective approaches in modern chemistry education. Virtual laboratories and interactive simulations help students understand chemical processes more clearly through visual representation. Such tools also make the educational experience more engaging and support the development of students' research and analytical skills. The integration of these technologies is especially useful in grades 7–8, when students begin to study the fundamental concepts of chemistry and foster their interest in the subject. Thus, the implementation of educational platforms in chemistry teaching can significantly improve the quality of chemistry education and contribute to the development of students' scientific thinking.

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